

NCW EXPOSED

PROMOTING LEGAL TERRORISM (NCW AN AGENT OF WCD)

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NCW: The National Commission for Women was set up as statutory body in January 1992 under the National Commission for Women Act, 1990 (Act No. 20 of 1990 of Govt of India) to :

- Review the Constitutional and Legal safeguards for women;
- Recommend remedial legislative measures;
- Racilitate redressal of grievances and
- Advise the Government on all policy matters affecting women.

TOTAL BUDGET OF 2020: 29664.90 Crore Rupees.

I. महिला और बाल विकास मंत्रालय के संबंध में 31 मार्च, 2020 को समाप्त होने वाले वर्ष में व्यय के लिये आवश्यक धनराशि का अनुमान।
 I. Estimates of the amount required in the year ending 31st March, 2020 to defray charges in respect of **MINISTRY OF WOMEN AND CHILD DEVELOPMENT**

	राजस्व Revenue	पूंजी Capital	जोड़ Total	(₹ करोड़) (In ₹ crores)
भारित Charged :	
स्वीकृत Voted :	29664.89	0.01	29664.90	

II. शीर्ष जिनके अन्तर्गत महिला और बाल विकास मंत्रालय की ओर से इस अनुदान का हिसाब दिखाया जाएगा।
 II. The Heads under which this Grant will be accounted for on behalf of the **MINISTRY OF WOMEN AND CHILD DEVELOPMENT**

मुख्य शीर्ष Major Head	वास्तविक 2017-2018 Actuals	बजट अनुमान 2018-2019 Budget Estimates	संशोधित अनुमान 2018-2019 Revised Estimates	बजट अनुमान 2019-2020 Budget Estimates
राजस्व भाग REVENUE SECTION				
सचिवालय-सामाजिक सेवाएं Secretariat-Social Services	2251	42.83	43.62	44.42
सामाजिक सुरक्षा और कल्याण Social Security and Welfare	2235	3187.69	3998.69	2797.54
पोषाहार Nutrition	2236	12.12	14.00	13.20
पूर्वोत्तर क्षेत्र North Eastern Areas	2552	...	2445.39	2451.27
राज्य सरकारों को सहायता अनुदान Grants-in-aid to State Governments	3601	17116.29	18355.96	19635.32
संघ राज्य क्षेत्र की सरकारों को सहायता अनुदान Grants-in-aid to Union Territory Governments	3602	148.21	342.33	271.74
जोड़ - राजस्व भाग Total-Revenue Section		20507.14	25199.99	25213.49
पूंजी भाग CAPITAL SECTION				
सामाजिक सुरक्षा और कल्याण पर पूंजी परिव्यय Capital Outlay on Social Security and Welfare	4235	13.31	0.01	45.13
जोड़ - पूंजी भाग Total-Capital Section		13.31	0.01	45.13
कुल जोड़ GRAND TOTAL		20520.45	25200.00	25258.62

टिप्पणी: उपरोक्त अनुमानों में नीचे दिखाई गई वसूलियां शामिल नहीं हैं, जिन्हें व्यय में से घटा कर खालों में समायोजित कर दिया जाता है।

Question is what WCD/NCW do with 29664.89 Crore Money?

Few years back former union minister for women and child development Maneka Gandhi said that the role of men in gender sensitisation was critical since "**All the violence is male-generated**".

News Source : <https://www.hindustantimes.com/india/all-violence-is-male-generated-maneka-gandhi/story-QzBDLrEhuCOr5Rjst9KD4O.html>

This shows hatred towards men, WCD/NCW has no policy to make any home happy home, instead they promote domestic Violence. There is not a single event NCW promoted make a marriage successful. Instead minister spit venom calling men as All violence is generated by Men.

WCD/NCW always claim 498A IPC or PWDVA is not misused when now and then someone raise this issue if so;
why do they not allow camera and cctv in mediation centers and women's police stations where they force men to agree to women demand?

Why they oppose Punishment for filling False 498A IPC or PWDVA and innocent men and his family acquitted?

In 2015 when Indian government planning to Amend dowry law (IPC 498A) WCD/NCW along with senior Supreme Court lawyer Indira Jaising strongly opposed, terming Women need freehand to misuse the law.

The Law Commission recommended that the offence under Section 498A should be made a compoundable offence with the permission of Court.

Justice Malimath Committee on Criminal Justice Reform also recommended that it should be made compoundable as well as bailable.

Last year, the Home Ministry had asked all state governments to be judicious in slapping Section 498A of IPC in matrimonial disputes as the provision may be used as "weapons rather than shields by disgruntled wives".

Opposing the move to dilute the anti-dowry provision of the law, senior Supreme Court lawyer Indira Jaising said it is a law which gives relief and protection to harassed woman and it should be continued.

"Violence against women is a violation of human rights. There is no compromise of that. I would disagree with the government move," says Jaising

News Source : <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/politics-and-nation/government-plans-to-amend-anti-dowry-harassment-law/articleshow/46571163.cms>

In 2017, Supreme Court judgment on Sec 498A (Rajesh Sharma & Ors. Vs State of UP & Anr., Crl. Appeal. No. 1265/2017) and the Minister of Women and Child Development Maneka Gandhi's order on setting up windows for men who allege that false cases have been filed against them., it was eyewash to media and world and WCD/NCW never heard any complaint from men.

Many women organizations who mint money by providing false statistics to WCD/NCW to get financial support opposed to dilution of 498A, The petitioners said women's organisations and others who work on the ground with women survivors of violence, such as the Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Swayam, Shramajibi Mahila Samiti and Vimochana, said "Judicial decisions regarding women's right to a life of dignity and free of violence, both physical and mental, in the matrimonial home, cannot be premised on hearsay, and anecdotes echoing

embedded prejudice,” they said, urging the authorities to take all necessary steps to ensure that women’s access to justice is not diluted or obstructed.

In her response, Lalitha Kumaramangalam, Chairperson, NCW, said “it is necessary to delink the emotional issues being raised on misuse of Section 498A and argue for its effective use on purely legal logic and rationale,” said a release issued by rights organisations.

So, WCD/NCW not only call All men are violent but oppose punishment for misusers of law 498A IPC or PWDVA, they not only protecting women who misuse law but Promote **LEGAL TERRORISM** also.

Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961 with the intention of protecting wives from marital violence (cruelty to married women), abuse and extortionist dowry demands, but this law is drafted so cunningly, that many Girl families gives money as stridhan, it’s a other word for Dowry to keep girl side safe from section 3 of Dowry Prohibition Act, but marriage turn soar same stridhan they term it as Dowry and man demanded it, and the history of this law not a single Women is charged under DP3 so far.

Not only women is protected under DP3 but force accused men to prove all baseless allegation on him. All this was done in accordance with 91st Report of the Law Commission of India (1983) on ‘Dowry Deaths and Law Reform; Amending the Hindu Marriage Act, 1955 the Indian Penal Code, 1860 and the Indian evidence Act, 1872’41, and 185th Report of the Law Commission of India (March 2003) on Review of the Indian Evidence Act, 1872. Even in this case, where a person is prosecuted for taking or abetting dowry or for demanding dowry, the burden of proof was placed solely on the accused.

Why WCD/NCW oppose dilution of 498A IPC or PWDVA or punishment for misusing because they show the FIR figure to get Funds from the Government. It’s a bread and butter for them, if 498A IPC or PWDVA diluted and ask women to prove her all false allegation and if found false if she punished, total Fir count will be reduced.

Cases under Section 498A was found to have the lowest conviction rate — merely 12.1 per cent — among all cases of crimes against women.

According to the latest data on crimes, released by the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), more than 3.3 lakh cases of crimes against women were

registered in 2016. Of these, 1.1 lakh cases related to ‘Cruelty by husband or his relatives’.

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“Assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty”, kidnapping, and rape, which formed the next three major chunks of crimes against women, had conviction rates of 21.8%, 21.4% and 25.5% in 2016, according to NCRB.

Close to 10,000 cases were also registered under the Dowry Prohibition Act in 2016, but conviction rate here too was just over 15%.

(News source : <https://indianexpress.com/article/india/section-498a-dowry-most-firs-least-convictions-4969913/>)

NCRB data shows 85% Dowry Prohibition Act are fake but WCD/NCW nowhere shows how many cases men are acquitted. They only show how many complaints are filed. **NOW YOU KNOW WHY WCD/NCW OPPOSE DILUTION OF THESE LAWS.**

Not only WCD/NCW promote Legal terrorism, oppose dilution of these laws, Women ministry also claim "Many women suffering abuse want to go to their mother's house, but during the lockdown, they can only be sent to state-run shelter homes, where the risk of overcrowding and poor hygiene runs high."

When WCD/NCW has **29664.90 Crore Rupees** of yearly funding why these shelter homes are unhygienic ?

(News source : <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2020/04/locked-abusers-india-domestic-violence-surge-200415092014621.html>)

If any anyone want to test our claim, can call them for help, If a women really harassed and if she call for Help, that help never arrive. If she is a elderly then not at all. Here is proof of our claim.

This is a letter from WCD/NCW says elderly women is not coming under their mandate.

भारत सरकार
GOVERNMENT OF INDIA
राष्ट्रीय महिला आयोग
NATIONAL COMMISSION FOR WOMEN
4, दीन दयाल उपाध्याय मार्ग
4, DEEN DAYAL UPADHYAYA MARG
नई दिल्ली-110 002
NEW DELHI-110 002
Website : www.ncw.nic.in

LETTER

CASE NO. 8/C0500721/VT/MSH/NEW/2006

DATED - February 03, 2007

The complaint filed by Mrs.

To,

Address - Post Box No.
Karkala Post Udupi,
District Udupi, Karnataka - 574104.

Dear Madam/Sir,

I am directed to refer to your complaint which was placed before the Commission.

Thereafter, upon perusing the complaint, the Commission has passed the following order -

Your matter/complaint does not fall under the mandate of the Commission.

Hence, the case has been closed by the Commission and you are accordingly informed.

ANJALI PATHAK
(CO-ORDINATOR)

As per WCD/NCW only young women are coming under mandate, Older women, Mother-in-laws are not Women.

Recently on twitter, NCW created a poll regarding the gender facing the domestic violence. But when the poll results was showing men as highest percentage domestic violence victims, the poll itself was IMMEDIETLY deleted by NCW.

<https://twitter.com/NCWIndia/status/1263765495016124418?s=19> (NOW DELETED – Actual Twitter link)

NCW
@NCWIndia

Cast your poll 1/5

For [@NCWIndia](#) next Live Session on 'Bystander Intervention' with [@kapoors_s](#) [@SayftyCom](#) - we are running a poll to understand some of - [#BystanderEffect](#)

1. Who is usually at risk of harassment?

1,016 votes • 16 hours 38 minutes left

3:05 PM · 22 May 20 · [Twitter Web App](#)

WCD/NCW has 29664.90 Crore Rupees (2020) Government Funding, anyone can guess what they do with that money? Why no real women is not getting any help? There are many women approach Men's NGO like MyNation Hope Foundation,

asking for help, WCD/NCW is scam ministry, same was reported here. These are not our finding but from well know news media.

90% of NGOs seeking funds under WCD scheme found fake

NEW DELHI: In a disturbing revelation, the women and child development (WCD) ministry has found that nearly 90% of around 1,400 NGOs seeking financial grants under a major training and employment scheme were fake.

Top officials in the ministry said applications were invited from NGOs to impart skill development training to women in rural areas under its Support to Training and Employment Programme (STEP) which has a corpus of Rs 30 crore.

"We had received 1,400 to 1,500 applications of which 90% are fake. The scrutiny of applications revealed that most of the NGOs have applied multiple times giving false names and details," a senior official said. STEP is a major programme being implemented by WCD ministry, aimed at providing employability skills to women. The official said the ministry has decided to upload the names of all fake NGOs on its website so that they can be "exposed" and "identified" by other ministries as well.

(News Source : <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/centre-ngo/90-of-NGOs-seeking-funds-under-WCD-scheme-found-fake/articleshow/46790570.cms>)

Not only this WCD/NCW keep on inventing new ways to make money, Get funds creating useless survey/study/research etc. here is yet another new scheme to ask money from government. They are getting crores of funds for last 30 years still they have not done these studies, which they keep on repeating again and again

Next exposure target of WCD/NCW -

<http://ncwapps.nic.in/WriteReadData/ScanDocuments/Eproposals/OfficeOrder/GuidelinesFY2019202001082019.pdf>

But they forgot to add their actual business modules.

HOW TO MAKE EASY MONEY FILLING FAKE 498A / PWDVA CASES.

HOW TO KILL HUSBAND AND NOT GET CAUGHT.

HOW TO HARASS AGED IN-LAWS AND KICK THEM OUT OF THEIR OWN HOUSE.

Hundreds of news reports of Killing of Men by their wives reported in this study report for the year 2020.

(Ref: <https://mynation.net/voice/study-report-dv-on-men/>)

Still some Judges/Ministers says, Time has not come to make laws for men
(News Source : <https://www.livelaw.in/webinar/we-have-not-reached-the-point-where-men-need-protection-from-women-justice-hima-kohli-158147>)

THIS IS THE REAL FACE OF WCD/NCW.

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Disclaimer: This Research study does not used any Fake statistics to justify any views expressed by the authors, Most Statistics used can be found on NCRB, respective Government Ministry websites or on medico legal Journals.